

did not support pathovar growth up to 10 d incubation. *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola* is generally less susceptible to antibiotics such as 0.001% amoxycillin, 0.001% ampicillin, or 0.005% neomycin than *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae*. None of the phenotypic features was correlated with the virulence of the strains. It was not possible to phenotypically differentiate the pathogenic races or groups of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae*.

Brown blotch strains share many features with *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* and pv. *oryzicola*. They are singly-occurring gram-negative rods; they metabolize glucose oxidatively; they are catalase positive, indole negative, urease negative, nitrate reductase negative; they produce acid from D-glucose, are strictly aerobic, and do not utilize L-asparagine as sole C and N source. However, there are some striking differences between BB and BLS pathogens (see table). Besides those features, the following tendencies for differentiation exist: brown blotch isolates

Differentiation between the bacteria causing BB, BLS, and brown blotch on rice, RUG-IRRI.

	BB (<i>X. campestris</i> pv. <i>oryzae</i>)	BLS (<i>X. campestris</i> pv. <i>oryzicola</i>)	Brown blotch
Acetoin production	-	+	-
Oxidase	-	-	-
H ₂ S from peptone	+	+	-
Hydrolysis of TWEEN 60 and 80	+	+	-
Growth on L-alanine as sole C source	-	+	+
Growth on glycerol or sodium propionate as sole C source	-	-	+
Growth on 0.2% vitamin-free casamino acids	-	+	+
Growth on Kado and Heskett's selective medium	-	-	+
Resistance towards			
0.001% Cu(NO ₃) ₂	+	-	+
0.001% 8-hydroxyquinoline	-	-	+
0.001% ZnO	-	-	+

are gelatinase negative against 49% positives for *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* and 100% for *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola*, do not hydrolyze arbutin (91% and 67% positives), and are erythromycin resistant (0% and 7%).

Furthermore, they grow luxuriantly on Döbereiner N-free medium. DNA:rRNA hybridizations and % G+C determination showed that brown blotch isolates definitely do not belong in *Xanthomonas*. □

Severe ufra outbreak in transplanted rice in Bangladesh

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The transplanted rice crop in the 5,000-ha Dhaka-Narayanganj-Demra (DND) irrigation project area, about 20 km southeast of Dhaka, was badly infested by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*, which causes ufra disease. Transplanted rice is continuously cropped in the project area except in some high elevation fields where mustard is grown in dry season. Symptoms

were white-splash pattern chlorosis, brown spots on leaves and culms at the growing points, and delayed panicle emergence.

Sporadic ufra attacks were first reported in early 1979. Disease incidence has gradually increased, with occasional severe outbreaks (see table). In Sep 1984 almost all fields were affected, with 5-100% infestation. Severity ranged from mild chlorosis to panicle nonemergence. Some plots were destroyed and farmers cut the plants for hay.

Most farmers used no ufra control, although a few used furadan at one-third the recommended dose of 33 kg/ha or 1.0 kg ai/ha. Fields previously planted to

mustard were least affected. About 7.5% of production (7,000-8,000 t) may be lost. Preliminary results of experiments with potted plants indicate that recommended doses of furadan, disulfoton, or fenamiphos applied to soil or as a foliar spray may cure infested plants. □

Bacterial leaf streak (BLS) incidence in Nellore, Andhra Pradesh

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In late kharif 1983-84, a serious BLS outbreak, caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola*, occurred at Nellore for the first time. We surveyed farmers fields from Sep to Dec 1983 to assess disease severity.

The first BLS symptoms were observed the first week of Oct on 50- to 80-d-old, NLR9672, although all varieties developed typical symptoms. Varieties grown on smaller areas include NLR9674, NLR27999, and BCP.1. All the varieties

Estimated ufra severity and yield loss over several years in the DND project area, Bangladesh.

Year	Crop ^a	Infested fields (%)	Severity as % infested plants	Yield loss (%)
1978	T. aman	20-30	10-40	10
1981	Born	10-15	10-20	5
	T. aman	10-15	10-20	5
1982	Boro	10-15	10-20	5
	T. aman	20-25	10-40	10
1983	Boro	20-25	10-20	5
	T. aman	40-50	30-100	50
1984	Born	40-50	30-40	40
	T. aman	90-100	60-100	60-75

^a T. aman = transplanted aman.

cultivated were susceptible, scoring 9 on the Standard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale. At the end of Oct, the disease was widespread, with rice in many fields showing coalesced lesions on the leaves

and blighting. Disease incidence was severe in Nov, when round beads of bacterial ooze were observed on badly infected leaves. Disease incidence declined in Dec, probably because of relatively

lower temperatures (27°C-21°C).

There was 323 mm rainfall in Sep and 148.8 mm in Oct, with favorable temperatures and humidity for disease development. □

Pest control and Management INSECTS

Deterrent effects of seed oil and extracts of some meliaceae plants on rice gall midge (GM) oviposition

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We evaluated seed oil of neem *Azadirachata indica*, and seed oil and methanol (M) and petroleum ether (PE) extracts of chinaberry *Melia azedarach* and *M. toosendan* as oviposition deterrents of GM *Orseolia oryzae*, a serious rice pest in China and tropical Asia.

Egg laying decreased in choice and no-choice tests when gravid GM females were caged on rice seedlings sprayed with seed oils or extracts. In the no-choice test, a 2% M-extract of *M. toosendan* and *M. azedarach* reduced egg laying by 96% and 71% (Table 1). In the choice test, a 1% M-extract of *M. toosendan* and *M. azedarach* seed kernel reduced oviposition by 96% and 83%. The PE-extract of chinaberry seed kernels also deterred oviposition. In the no-choice test, a 2% spray application of neem oil or *M. toosendan* oil reduced oviposition by 47% and 85%, but oil application was not as effective in the choice test. However, both M- and PE-extracts sprayed at 1 to 3% concentration significantly reduced the incidence of silvershoots (Table 2). Preliminary inves-

Table 1. Repellent effect of a spray application of 2% emulsified seed oil or extract of chinaberry and neem on GM oviposition, Guangzhou, China, Sep 1983.^a

Treatment (T)	Eggs laid/replication (no.)	Unlaid eggs ^b /female (no.)	Oviposition deterrence ^c (%)
<i>M. toosendan</i> oil	93 b	4 ab	30
<i>M. toosendan</i> PE-extract	52 c	20 a	61
<i>M. toosendan</i> M-extract	6 d	11 ab	96
<i>M. azedarach</i> oil	20 cd	13 ab	85
<i>M. azedarach</i> PE-extract	15 d	10 ab	88
<i>M. azedarach</i> M-extract	39 c	19 a	71
<i>A. indica</i> oil	44 c	2 ab	67
Control (C) (solvent only)	133 a	0 b	0

^aNo-choice test conducted in 6 × 6 cm plastic cups using 12-d-old rice seedlings. Av of 10 replications for each treatment; means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. ^bThe number of unlaid eggs was determined by dissecting GM females shortly after they died. ^cDeterrence (%) = $\frac{C-T}{C} \times 100$; T = eggs laid in the treatment, C = eggs laid in the control.

Table 2. Effect of spray application of 3% emulsified seed oil and extracts of chinaberry and neem on the incidence of silvershoots caused by GM, Guangzhou, China, Oct 1983.^a

Treatment	Seedlings/replication (no.)	Silvershoots/replication (no.)	Silvershoots (%)
<i>M. toosendan</i> oil	75	4	5 b
<i>M. toosendan</i> PE-extract	81	2	2 b
<i>M. toosendan</i> M-extract	76	3	4 b
<i>M. azedarach</i> oil	95	5	5 b
<i>M. azedarach</i> PE-extract	82	3	4 b
<i>M. azedarach</i> M-extract	88	4	4 b
<i>A. indica</i> oil	77	5	6 b
Control (solvent only)	67	18	27 a

^aTrial conducted on 21-d-old rice seedlings grown in a greenhouse. Av of 7 replications for each treatment; means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

tigations showed that neem and chinaberry oils and extracts at 3% concentration had little ovicidal action.

Field trials are underway to evaluate the potential of these plant derivatives in rice insect pest management. □

Integrated control of rice gall midge (GM)

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To follow up earlier experiments, we conducted confirmatory field trials on inte-

grated control of GM *Orseolia oryzae* at the Regional Research Institute, Chiplima, in 1979 and 1980 wet seasons. Susceptible Jaya and resistant Shakti were planted the first week of Jul and fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. Promising chemical control schedules were tested in 100-m² plots. Untreated control plots were also

maintained.

The maximum protection treatment comprising seedling root dip in 0.02% ai isofenphos + 1% urea for 3 h; phorate granules broadcast at 1 kg ai/ha at 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting (DT) followed by quinalphos spray at 0.5 kg ai/ha at 85 DT gave excellent GM control (Table 1).